

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR TYPES

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Annotation: Technology provides instant access to the right information and develops important skills in working with sources. The value of the educational process is increased if the information in textbooks or teaching aids can be quickly updated and supplemented, including by the students themselves. Technology plays a big role in human life. Not always the material component plays a major role. Many IT-specialists confirm this. They call the most important plus of the industry not high salaries, but prospects and professional development. In IT, in fact, there are unlimited opportunities for growth.

Keywords: technology, art, mastery, skill, technology in technology, man-made objects, information technology, information, material production technology, material resources, photocopier, telefax, fax, scanner, computer and communication technology, ashery, mechanical technology, information technology of the office.

ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ИХ ВИДЫ

Аннотация: Технологии обеспечивают мгновенный доступ к нужной информации и воспитывают важные навыки по работе с источниками. Ценность учебного процесса повышается, если информация в учебниках или учебных пособиях может быстро обновляться и дополняться, в том числе силами самих учащихся. Технология играет большую роль в жизни человека. Далеко не всегда материальная составляющая играет главную роль. Многие IT-специалисты это подтверждают. Самым важным плюсом отрасли они называют не высокие зарплаты, а перспективность и профессиональное развитие. В IT, по сути, неограниченные возможности для роста.

Ключевые слова: технологии, Изобразительное искусство, Мастерство, умение, Технологии в технологиях, Искусственные объекты, информационные технологии, Информация, Технология производства материалов, Материальные ресурсы, Копировальный аппарат, Телефакс, Факс, Сканер, Компьютерные и коммуникационные технологии, Пепельница, Механическая технология, Информационные технологии офис.

AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNING TURLARI

Annotatsiya: Texnologiya to'g'ri ma'lumotlarga tezkor kirishni ta'minlaydi va manbalar bilan ishlashda muhim ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiradi. Darslik yoki o'quv qo'llanmalardagi ma'lumotlar, shu jumladan, o'quvchilarning o'zlari tomonidan tez yangilanishi va to'ldirilishi mumkin bo'lsa, ta'lim jarayonining ahamiyati ortadi. Texnologiya inson hayotida katta rol o'ynaydi. Har doim ham moddiy komponent asosiy rol o'ynamaydi. Ko'pgina IT-mutaxassislari buni tasdiqlaydilar. Ular sanoatning eng muhim plusini yuqori ish haqi emas, balki istiqbol va kasbiy rivojlanish deb atashadi. IT sohasida, aslida, o'sish uchun cheksiz imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, san'at, ustalik, malaka, texnikada texnologiya, sun'iy ob'ektlar, axborot texnologiyasi, axboriy ma'lumot, moddiy ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasi, moddiy resurslar, kseroks, telefaks, faks, skaner, kompyuter va kommunikatsion texnologiya, kullik, mexanik texnologiya, Ofis(idora)ning axborot texnologiyasi.

Technology translated from Greek, the word technology means art, mastery, skill. In technology, technology means a process that uses a set of methods, methods and tools to create a certain desired material product. Technology changes the initial state of the object and brings it to a state that meets a new, predetermined requirement.

Information technology is a process that uses a set of tools and methods for collecting, processing and transmitting data (primary information) to obtain new quality information about the state of an object, process or phenomenon (information product).

Information technology (IT) is a technology that:

- provide the solution of applied problems by methods of information processing;
- used to process information.

Computer-aided design, automated control, etc. can be cited as an example of information technologies. Usually, information technologies are implemented using computer technology that provides high data processing speed, fast information retrieval, data dispersal, access to information sources regardless of their location. Accordingly, computers and software can be cited as an example of means for implementing information technologies, the task of which is to transform, protect, transmit and receive information. Information technology and systems are essential to accounting and auditing.

2. Information technology database management systems

A database management system (DBMS) is a software system designed to create a common database on a computer that is used to solve many problems. Such systems serve to keep the database up to date and provide effective user access to the data contained in it within the limits of the authority granted to users. The DBMS is designed for centralized database management in the interests of all those working in this system.

The technology can be described as follows. Technology is the management of processes aimed at creating artificial objects. How well the conditions are created to ensure that the desired processes go in the desired direction indicates the efficiency of the technology. Here, natural processes are controlled not only to change the composition, structure and form of matter, but also to process information and create new information. Therefore, information technology can be described as follows.

Information technology is the process of using a set of methods and means of information collection, processing and transmission, bringing information from one form to another, qualitatively new form.

The purpose of material production technology is to produce a new product that satisfies human demand. The purpose of information technology is to produce new information, which is necessary for a person to do something, analyze it and make a decision based on it. Using different technologies, different products can be obtained from the same material resources. The same can be said about information technology.

Various special equipment, machine tools, equipment, etc. are used in material production. Information technologies also have their own "equipment" and tools. These are xerox, telefax, fax, scanner and other tools. Information is processed and changed through these tools. Currently, computers and computer networks are widely used for information processing. Computer and communication technology are often used to emphasize the use of computers and computer networks in information technology.

Information technology is directly related to information systems, which are the main environment for it. Because information technology is an organized process that consists of performing operations, operations and algorithms of various complexity on the information available in information systems.

Information technology is one of the most important methods of rational use of society's information resources, and has gone through several evolutionary stages until now.

We will briefly touch on these stages.

Stage 1. It lasted until the second half of the 19th century. At this stage, "Kullik" information technology has developed. His tool: pen, inkwell, book. Communication, that is, communication is carried out from person to person or through mail.

Stage 2. The end of the 19th century, when "Mechanical" technology developed. Its main tool consists of a typewriter and an arithmetic meter.

Stage 3. Belonging to the beginning of the 20th century, "Electromechanical" differs in technology. As its main tools, telegraphs and telephones were used. At this stage, the purpose of information technology also changed. In it, the main emphasis was shifted from the form of information representation to the formation of its content.

Step 4. By the middle of the 20th century, it was determined by the use of "Electronic" technologies. The main means of these technologies are EHMs and automated control systems and information search systems based on them.

Step 5. It corresponds to the end of the 20th century. At this stage, "Computer" technologies have advanced. Their main tool is personal computers with software tools for various purposes. At this stage, a change of technical means for daily life, culture and other areas took place. Local and global computer networks began to be used.

Information technologies are divided into several types:

1. To the data processing information technologies. They are designed to solve problems that process initial data according to certain algorithms. For example, every company must have information technology that processes information about its employees.
2. Management information technologies. Their goal is to satisfy the demand for information of people whose work is related to decision-making. Management information systems include information about the past, present and future of the organization.
3. Information technology of the office.

In the course of studying subjects in general education schools, students will have the opportunity to use computer technologies in their practical activities in the future, when communicating directly with modern computer and information technology tools. At the same time, students' interest in new information technologies and their software will change significantly. This, in turn, makes it possible for students to

acquire deep enough knowledge not only of taught subjects, but also of computer and information technologies.

References:

1. <https://pandia.ru/text/80/199/41167.php>
2. <https://kompy.info/axborot-texnologiyalari-va-ularning-turlari.html>
3. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Axborot_texnologiyalari